

ISic0245

I.Sicily inscription 0245

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] Aponiu
2. [---] v(ixit) a(nnis) XXV
3. [---] p,a,t,e,r fîliae
4. [---]mae · fecit

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285324

EDR 127492

EDCS 10900670

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0789

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 172

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0245. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334709>